

**CO₂ storage by cyanobacteria
induced biomineralization in
presence of basaltic glass**

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AVERTISSEMENT

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RESUME

La biominéralisation de carbonate est un processus naturel souvent observé en présence de cyanobactéries. Il permet le stockage du CO₂ atmosphérique dans les minéraux précipités, à conditions que les concentrations en cations métalliques soient suffisantes. L'objectif de ce mémoire est de reproduire les conditions optimales pouvant amener à la précipitation de calcite ou de magnésite en présence de cyanobactéries. Des stocks contenant des cyanobactéries actives ou des cyanobactéries mortes ont été préparés dans le but de comparer leur impact sur la biominéralisation. Le fort taux de dissolution et l'abondance du verre basaltique sur la surface de la Terre en fait une source adéquate de cations Ca²⁺ et Mg²⁺. Les cyanobactéries utilisées appartiennent à l'espèce *Synechococcus* qui joue un grand rôle dans le processus de biominéralisation global sur Terre. Dans le but de se rapprocher au maximum des conditions naturelles, un système de « flow through reactor » a été choisi. Différentes concentrations ioniques ont été utilisées (0.1, 0.01 et 0.001 mg/L de NaNO₃) afin d'observer l'influence du NaNO₃ sur la dissolution et la biominéralisation. L'expérience de contrôle inorganique s'est effectuée à un pH neutre (pH<8). Aucune précipitation n'a donc été attendue. Dans le cadre des expériences organiques, les cyanobactéries augmentent le pH de l'environnement par le processus de biominéralisation, ce qui entraîne indirectement une plus grande formation de carbonate CO₃²⁻. Ces molécules réagissent ensuite avec les cations métalliques issus du verre basaltique dissout afin de précipiter de la calcite CaCO₃ ou de la magnésite MgCO₃. La présence de cyanobactéries actives a donc permis d'augmenter l'index de saturation (SI) pour la formation de calcite et de magnésite (de -10.56 à -9.48). Cependant les valeurs de SI restent négatives, dues aux faibles concentrations de Ca²⁺ et Mg²⁺ obtenues. Les cyanobactéries mortes jouent le rôle de sites de nucléations grâce à leur charge de surface négative qui attirent le bicarbonate HCO₃⁻ et les cations métalliques. Un SI plus proche de 0 a pu être observé dans ce cas, mais la présence de cyanobactéries actives reste indispensable pour obtenir un pH alcalin.

ABSTRACT

Cyanobacteria induced biomineralization is a natural process leading to carbonate nucleation while storing CO₂ from the air provided sufficient dissolved metal cations concentrations in the cell's environment. The purpose of this study is to reproduce optimum conditions in order to precipitate calcite or magnesite in presence of cyanobacteria. Active and dead cyanobacteria stocks were prepared to compare their different impact on biomineralization. Basaltic glass was chosen as a Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺ source, because of its abundance on Earth's surface and its adequate dissolution rate. The *Synechococcus* cyanobacteria species being a major actor of natural biomineralization on Earth, it has been used in these experiments. In order to have close conditions to the natural environment, a flow through reactor system has been chosen. Different nominal electrolyte backgrounds (0.1, 0.01 and 0.001 mol/L NaNO₃) were used to observe the NaNO₃ influence in dissolution and biomineralization. Inorganic control experiment showed that any precipitation can happen in a non-alkaline environment (pH <8). Active cyanobacteria were expected to alkalize the environment by the process of photosynthesis, indirectly enhancing the carbonate CO₃²⁻ formation which may react with dissolved cations to nucleate calcite CaCO₃ or magnesite MgCO₃. Active cells were shown to increase saturation index (SI) values with respect to both CaCO₃ and MgCO₃. Indeed, SI values increased from -10.56 to -9.48. However SI remains negative because of low calcium and magnesium cations activities. Dead cells were expected to act as nucleation site as their negative surface charge lead to the binding of elements such as HCO₃⁻ and metal cations to on their surface. SI values observed were closer to 0, but presence of active cyanobacteria is needed in order to alkalize the environment.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The raise of CO₂ concentration in the atmosphere is one of the most important environmental problems on Earth today arising from human activity. Carbon storage methods need to be developed urgently in order to reduce the CO₂ impact on Earth's terrestrial and aquatic environments. Previous studies have eluded at the ability of cyanobacteria to induce biomineralization of CO₂. This is an option which is still in its infancy and could possibly be used in the near-future to decrease atmospheric CO₂ levels.

Several studies have been already done, on the one hand to well understand cyanobacteria photosynthesis metabolism and its effect on his environment (McConnaughey, 1994; Lee *et al.*, 2004), and on the other hand to determine the optimum conditions for using minerals (e.g. basaltic glass, olivine) as a metal cation source (Oelkers, 2001; Oelkers *et Gislason*, 2003). The link between cyanobacteria photosynthesis and the presence of metal cations have been shown to lead to carbonate precipitation in suitable conditions. Those studies were related more precisely to cyanobacteria cells mechanisms against biomineralization at their surfaces, mineral dissolution or surface charge and zeta potential of active and dead cyanobacteria. Besides, other studies with closed problematics were made, by connecting cyanobacteria cells with different mineral sources (e.g. olivine).

The goal of this study is to quantify the rates of carbonate precipitation in the presence of basaltic glass and *Synechococcus* species cyanobacteria. These microorganisms are capable of maintaining an alkaline pH environment required for the solution suersaturation with respect to carbonates, as long as an efficient source of metal cations in present. Basaltic glass used in this study have been shown to dissolve efficiently at acidic and basic pH releasing Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺ in significant concentrations for the potential formation of carbonate phases.

2. STATE OF THE ART

2.1. Carbon cycle

In a half-century of observation, it has been shown that man is responsible for a significant increase in the atmospheric CO₂ concentration (Figure 1), leading to today's global warming. Recent reports from the IPCC (The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change) confirm with a 95% of certainty that global temperatures increases in recent decades have anthropic causes.

The combustion of fossil fuels (coal, oil, gas) led to an increase in the atmospheric CO₂ levels, from 280 mg/kg at the beginning of the industrial revolution in 1780 to 380 mg/kg today (Harris, 2010). More than half of the carbon dioxide produced over the last half-century currently resides in the atmosphere, the rest of it, has been absorbed by the ocean.

Figure 1 - Atmospheric CO₂ concentration (mg/kg) versus time (modified after Gerlach, 2011)

The first consequence of this increase is the greenhouse effect. Atmospheric CO₂ absorbs the infrared rays coming from the surface of the Earth and redistributes this energy towards soil, leading to a global warming. Moreover, carbon dioxide in the ocean forms carbonic acid and increases the acidity

of water. The ocean surface pH has thus increased by 0.1 units since the preindustrial time. The increasing activity nowadays may further enhance this level from 0.3 to 0.4 additional units (Moser, 2013).

These are the reason why numerous approaches of CO₂ storage are being currently developed. The first solutions were ocean and soil storage. These techniques are still in use today, since most of necessary technologies to required by these methods already exist. In the case of soil storage, three types of reservoirs have been taken into account: saline aquifers, existing gas and oil, oil fields and unmineable coal seams (Baines *et al.*, 2004). Carbon dioxide may be stored for more than 1000 years; however this requires precise procedures concerning the setting up and the use of injecting wells. The very significant injections and the corrosion caused by CO₂ can have negative impacts on these facilities as well as on properties of the reservoirs (Cailly *et al.*, 2005). Leaking risks are present in these facilities, for instance on the abandoned wells, the content CO₂ has been shown to increase from 10 to 30% above normal (West *et al.*, 2005).

Micro-organisms, especially cyanobacteria, play a very important role in the carbon cycle. Indeed, they are fundamental in the ecosystems, such as primary producers up to 90% (with also the chlorophyllian eucaryotes) of the aquatic ecosystems production (Price *et al.*, 2008). Storage using cyanobacteria carbonate biomineralization seems to be a promising approach since it is a reaction which is found on a large scale in nature. Biomineral sequestration has many advantages compared to the other methods of storage. It is a natural process whose reaction product is steady with a weak dismissal risk in atmosphere as long as the activity of cyanobacteria is maintained.

The carbon cycle presents two parts. One is known as “biological”, where carbon circulates quickly. The other one is known as “physicochemical”, where the circulation of carbonaceous flows is much slower (Sigg *et al.*, 2008). In the biological part, cyanobacteria are primary producers, implying that they transform inorganic carbon into organic matter thanks to photosynthesis, a mechanism profiting from solar energy. On the other hand, these organisms can also transform inorganic carbon into mineral carbon due to respiration as well as the fermentation. They ensure approximately half of carbon mineralization.

In the physicochemical process of the carbon cycle, there are exchanges between the different terrestrial envelopes (Figure 2). Indeed, carbon is found in various forms: (1) as carbonate minerals or organic matter in the lithosphere, (2) dissolved as HCO₃⁻ or CO₃²⁻ in the hydrosphere depending on the pH of the waters, (3) CO₂ in the atmosphere in very weak quantity, and finally (4) in the biosphere as carbon coming from the living organisms. Cyanobacteria are directly implicated in the diagenesis with carbonaceous rocks formation, in the origin of carbonates precipitation, as well as in weathering while taking part in the chemical degradation of various rock minerals (Baires *et al.*, 2004).

Several previous studies had shown the importance of basaltic glass and silicate rock weathering in the carbon cycle (Dessert *et al.*, 2002; Schott *et al.*, 2012; Schlesinger et Bernhardt, 2013). Indeed, basaltic glass and olivine are more easily weathered compared to others silicates. According to Gaillardet *et al.* (1999), weathering coming from continental basalts represents 30% to 35% of the global CO₂ consumption by silicate weathering. It represents around 4.08x10¹² mol/year of consumed carbon. Different parameters, such as runoff or temperatures, control chemical weathering. Vegetation cover and resulting soil solution compositions also plays a role in chemical weathering of

rocks when by generating acidic conditions and exposing rocks to a low pH (<7). This improves the mobility of cations (e.g. Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+}). More than 90% of the total Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} cations are released after weathering (Gislason *et al.*, 1996). The result is the conversion of CO_2 into bicarbonate in the ocean, which leads to carbonate precipitation (mostly induced by cyanobacteria), sedimentation and CO_2 storage.

Figure 2 - Simplified representation of the carbon global cycle (Modified after Stumm *et al.* 1996)

2.2 Cyanobacteria

2.2.1 Choice and presentation

Cyanobacteria are Gram-negative bacteria. They are photosynthetic and autotrophic organisms, generating organic matter by photosynthesis (Martinez *et al.*, 2010). Their photosynthetic system is similar to chlorophyllian plants. They proliferate in fresh water, in the ocean, as well as on dry land. Some species can even live under extreme conditions such as cold environment (Warwick, 2007), hot springs (Steunou *et al.*, 2006) or under heavy salt stress (Krumbein, 2004). They are the first prokaryotes appeared on Earth 3.0 to 2.8 Ga ago, and are believed to have generated the Great

Oxidation Event (GOE) at 2.4 to 2.2 Ga. During this time, a progressive enrichment of the Earth atmosphere with oxygen was suggested to be induced by the metabolic activity of oxygenic photosynthesis (Jansson *et al.*, 2010; Schirmer *et al.*, 2013; Holland, 2002).

Figure 3 shows cyanobacteria composition. Without an envelope, the cyanobacteria cell wall possesses two membranes (plasmic and external), where many external and internal elements transit thanks to various integrated transporters. According to Martinez *et al.* (2008, 2013), the Lipo-Polysaccharides layer (or S-layer) of 10 to 100 nm, located beyond the external membrane, contains “deprotonated” surface groups. These would include carboxyl ($>COO^- + H^+$), phosphate ($>PO_4^{3-} + H^+$) or hydroxyl ($>OH^- + H^+$). As these groups deprotonate, they are able to generate a net negative charge and attract some metal cations (e.g. Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+}). The inside aqueous solution composing within cytosol, contains elements such as thylakoides where the photosynthetic systems are situated, as well as carboxysomes where inorganic carbon is assimilated during photosynthesis.

Figure 3 - Cyanobacteria composition. (Modified after Parikh *et Madamwar*, 2006)

2.2.2 *Synechococcus* cyanobacteria species

The *Synechococcus* species used in this study is most representative of seawater cyanobacteria. It's an unicellular coccoid cyanobacteria containing outermost surface layers (S-layers), but no cell covering sheath (Moser *et al.*, 2013). This organism is often associated with the CO_2 biomineralization, since it represents a large part of the carbon binding in the ocean. Indeed, these species is associated with *Prochlorococcus*, which represents about 30% of the global photosynthesis. This makes the study of the carbonate mineral formation mechanisms by these cyanobacteria a very interesting subject from the biological and ecological points of view (Price *et al.*, 2008).

2.3 Surface charge and zeta potential of metabolically active and dead cyanobacteria

The net surface charge of active and dead cyanobacteria plays a significant role in maintaining the cell optimal functions and the regulation of processes like photosynthesis and mineral nucleation on the cell surface. This charge can be approximated thanks by the zeta potential. This refers to the electric potential difference between the diffuse layer of aqueous ions near the colloid surface, called the Stern-Layer, and the stationary layer of dissolved ions electrostatically interacting with the negatively or positively charged cell surface. This potential difference at the cell surface micro-environment varies depending on whether the cells are dead or metabolically active.

Martinez *et al.* (2008) showed that for active cyanobacteria, the surface charge is positive for a pH between pH values ranging from 8 to 10, with a zeta potential of about +12 mV (Figure 5). Indeed, at alkaline conditions, the positive charge is believed to be generated by the activity of the so called “H⁺-pump” a mechanism that release a proton on the cell surface. This mechanism succeeds in attracting the HCO₃⁻ towards the cyanobacteria surface. The maximum zeta potential was achieved with pH 9. This value almost corresponds to the maximum bicarbonate concentration. Figure 4 shows the carbonate concentration as a function of pH. These conditions are expected to reach super-saturation.

Figure 4 - Bjerrum plot of the change in carbonate system of seawater (modified after Ridgwell, 2005)

The dead cyanobacteria surface charge is negative, with zeta potentials in the order of -30 mV (Figure 5). This range will apt for the binding of positively charged metal cations, allowing inactive cyanobacteria to act as nucleation sites for carbonate minerals. The appearance of “deprotonated” surface groups would enhance the interaction of metal cations with the cyanobacteria cell surface.

The zeta potential study highlights the existence of a protection mechanism which would enable to prevent the active cyanobacteria from acting as nucleation sites for carbonates. This would cause mineral precipitation near their surface by inorganic mechanisms following the laws mineral

nucleation and crystal growth under appropriate supersaturated conditions. It is necessary for the cell to attract bicarbonate for photosynthesis, while remaining secure from mineral encrustation of their surface in the presence of sufficient metal cation (Ca^{2+} or Mg^{2+}) concentrations. The positive zeta potential was shown to decrease in the presence of HCO_3^- , and is increased by Ca^{2+} or Mg^{2+} cations. This shows a sustained positive surface charge maintained as a consequence of the cyanobacteria metabolism, thus protecting the cell from an uncontrolled carbonates precipitation directly on their surface.

This mechanism also improves the rate of inorganic carbonate biomineralization in cyanobacteria living in natural environments, since the bicarbonate attracted by the positive surface charge is used in calcification process managed by the cell.

Figure 5 : Zeta potential measurement showing a positive surface charge for active cells (White squares) and no change in surface charge inactive cells (black squares), (Martinez *et al.*, 2008).

2.3 Photosynthesis

Photosynthesis has a key role in carbonate precipitation by cyanobacteria. *Synechococcus* is an autotrophic and photolithotrophic organism carrying out the oxygenic photosynthesis. Using light as energy, it creates its own organic matter by reducing CO_2 (Schubert *et al.*, 1997). H_2O is the oxidized element giving the electron needed in this transformation. The pigment chlorophyll a is the reaction center of the photosystem. Phycobilines are components of the thylakoid membrane, able to interact with light photons. The inorganic carbon absorbed is synthesized according to the Calvin-Benson cycle (Figure 6) thanks to the Rubisco (Ribulose Biphosphate Carboxylase Oxygenase). This

enzyme, considered as the most abundant protein in the world, is the initial CO₂-fixing-enzyme of photosynthesis (Spreitzer *et al.*, 2002).

Figure 6 - Calvin-Benson Cycle. (Modified after Fridlyand *et al.*, 1999)

According to Fridlyand and *al.* (1999), the cycle in figure 5 consists in 4 steps :

1. 3 CO₂ molecules are assimilated by the Rubisco, creating a phosphoglyceric acid
2. ATP (Adenosine triphosphate) and NADPH (Nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide phosphate) are chemical substances. They permit to form glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate with the phosphoglyceric acid previously formed.
3. Glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate (G-3-P) is an organic compound formed and used by the cyanobacteria as an immediate food nutrient. Remaining compounds form 3 ribulose-5-phosphate molecules.
4. ATP transforms those molecules into 3 ribulose-bisphosphate (RuBP) which form, with CO₂, phosphoglyceric acid. The Calvin-Benson cycle can then repeat the first steps.

Photosynthesis can be then summarized as :

Schubert *et al.* (1997) showed the existence of two different phases in the oxygenic photosynthesis: a photochemical and a chemical part (Figure 7).

Figure 7 - Oxygenic photosynthesis (Modified after Green et al., 1996)

Figure (8) shows the two different systems used in the photochemical process, inside the thylakoid:

- The photosystem II with a high redox potential ($E^\circ = 0.81\text{V}$), uses the $\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{O}_2$ redox reaction. Using the energy from light photons, it sends the electrons to photosystem I.
- The photosystem I with a low redox potential ($E^\circ = -0.32\text{V}$), reduces the NADPH/NADP couple. NADPH is then used in the chemical part (Figure 7).
- From the thylakoid, the ATP synthase gives a single phosphate molecule Pi to the ADP which permits it to change into Adenosine triphosphate (ATP) which is used by cyanobacteria in the chemical phase (Figure 7)

Figure 8 - Cyanobacteria's photosynthetic chain (Modified after Schubert et al., 1997)

The chemical part takes place in the stroma and the cytoplasm. CO₂ enters the carboxysome. This micro-compartment has a diameter of 100 to 500 nm and contains the Rubisco (Ribulose Biphosphate Carboxylase Oxygenase).

All the chemical and photochemical reactions (Figure 7) happening in the cyanobacteria permit to assimilate CO₂ in the RuBP (3 ribulose-bisphosphate). The Calvin-Benson Cycle (Figure 6) also leads to the formation of organic matter (glucose) and water. The Rubisco has a respiration function which prompts to the emission of CO₂, assimilating oxygen (Spreitzer *et al.*, 2002).

2.4 Carbon concentrating mechanism CCM

In order to carry out photosynthesis, cyanobacteria require a constant supply of inorganic carbon (Ci), which comes from carbon dioxide CO₂ dissolution and bicarbonate HCO₃⁻ or CO₃²⁻ depending on the solution pH (Martinez *et al.*, 2010). A metabolic system is used by cyanobacteria to overcome the challenge presented by trying to attain Ci from an aqueous environment. Indeed, it permits to attract Ci inside the cell.

The Carbon-Concentrating-Mechanism (CCM) is an environmental adaptation of cyanobacteria (Price *et al.*, 2008), that leads to the transport and the stock of Ci inside cell. A highly-concentrated inorganic carbon rate is assured by the Rubisco, prompting to a better rate of photosynthesis fixation. CCM leads to intracellular inorganic carbon concentrations in excess of 1000 times the extracellular concentrations (Lee *et al.*, 2004). Indeed, CO₂ and HCO₃⁻ supplies are the most important nutritional supply known by cyanobacteria, apart from the energy from derived from sunlight (Figure 9).

Figure 9 - Model of the carbon concentration mechanism (CCM) and calcification in a cyanobacterial cell (Modified after Jansson *et al.*, 2010).

Jansson *et Northen* (2010) showed two different Ci supplies:

- Two CO₂ uptake systems have been identified, which allows carbon dioxide to diffuse to the cell's cytosol. NADPH dehydrogenase (NDH) complexes are located in the thylakoide's membrane (Figure 9) converts CO₂ into bicarbonate HCO₃⁻.
- If inorganic carbon is not provided by CO₂, HCO₃⁻ becomes an external resource of Ci. Indeed HCO₃⁻ is the most consumed form of carbon used by cyanobacteria. Three HCO₃⁻ transporters are located in both plasma and outer membranes. These proteins are able to assimilate bicarbonate into the cell. The active transport of HCO₃⁻ is also dependent on the extra-ATP generated during photosynthesis.

The large amount of bicarbonate present in the cytosol is integrated in the carboxysome (Figure 9). The carbonic anhydrase is a reaction enzyme located in this micro-compartment which re-converts all the bicarbonate to CO₂. A single proton H⁺ is consumed by each of these reactions, coupled with the reject of a hydroxide ion (OH⁻) outside the cell. The remaining CO₂ is the only substrate supported by the Rubisco which is then assimilated by the Calvin-Benson cycle (Jansson *et Northen*, 2010).

RubisCO does not assimilate the totality of the CO₂. Some of it exits the carboxysome. In this case, those molecules are recycled and reintroduced with the Rubisco (Price *et al.*, 2008). The constant exchange flow of OH⁻/H⁺ at the cell surface permits the regulation of the pH inside and outside the cyanobacteria.

2.5 Cyanobacteria induced biomineralization

CO₂ biomineralization is often found in lakes, seas and oceans in the form of calcium carbonate precipitation, where both polymorphs of this mineral (e.g. calcite and aragonite) can be observed (Jansson *et Northen*, 2010). The mechanisms by which cyanobacteria is able to influence the solution conditions to generate the necessary supersaturated conditions for carbonate precipitation in aquatic ecosystems must be better quantified and understood.

Biomineralization is a precipitation mechanism where the mineral dissolution permits the formation of a secondary mineral. This precipitation only occurs when external cations coming from the dissolution of a primary mineral (e.g. Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺) react with the environment created by a bacteria cell metabolism or charged surface (Merz-Preis, 2000).

Carbonate nucleation may take place on the dead cyanobacteria cell wall which has been shown to have a negative charge and can therefore act as a cation adsorption-site, and eventually a nucleation site for precipitation of carbonates. Minerals tend to precipitate by stratification on the external cell surface. Stromatolites are a good example of biomineralization (Riding, 2006). Indeed, they are microbial communities (cyanobacteria, bacteria, algae), formed through trapping, binding and calcification process. Stromatolites, are sedimentary rock, in the form of fine laminated layers, domes, and columns (Riding, 1999). Carbonate cyanobacteria biomineralization can't occur in a non-alkaline environment where pH is under 5, as cyanobacteria can't live in an acidic environment.

Photosynthesis and CCM are the first steps to calcification. If HCO_3^- is the cyanobacteria principal inorganic carbon resource, photosynthesis and calcification follow a molar ratio of 1 for 1. (McConnaughey, 1994)

The CCM mechanism can lead to bicarbonate absorption and hydroxide ion release, causing an alkaline pH near the cell surface micro-environment, which allows HCO_3^- to deprotonate into carbonate ions CO_3^{2-} and to increase saturation index. Figure 9 shows that the presence of both CO_3^{2-} and Ca^{2+} or Mg^{2+} cations permits the carbonates to nucleate in the form of calcite (CaCO_3) or magnesite (MgCO_3) (Riding, 2006). In the case of active cyanobacteria, the positive surface charge prevents cyanobacteria from a nucleation on its cell wall (Martinez *et al.*, 2010). Indeed, nucleation occurs in the environment as a deposition. Dead cyanobacteria may permit nucleation on cell walls as the surface charge is negative.

Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} cations interact with the negatively charged external cyanobacteria's wall where precipitation can occur after the first step of mineral nucleations. Those external layers are the extracellular polymeric substance (EPS) and the S-layer. The EPS is a class of polymers formed by some organic substances as proteins, polysaccharides, nucleic acids, lipids (Parikh *et al.*, 2006). The pH of those layers stay alkaline due to the activity of the carbonic anhydrase and they both are parts of the micro-environment created by the CCM.

The Photosynthetic Electron Transport (PET) and the antiports (Figure 9), which transport ions through the cell, have a major role in the rise of alkalinity in the EPS and S-layer. The transport of Ca^{2+} outside the cell and H^+ inside permits to maintain a constant concentration of Ca^{2+} near the cell surface (Obst *et al.*, 2009). This equilibrium can be changed by the alkalinity leading to a higher concentration of HCO_3^- and CO_3^{2-} due to the supply of CO_2 or the leak of these ion to the outside of the cell. Some acids are present in the EPS and S-layer such as glucamate and aspartate. When Ca^{2+} concentration is high, they are used as Ca^{2+} fixation-site (Rochaix, 2011).

In the presence of active cyanobacteria, biomineralization is induced by the metabolic activity. Active cyanobacteria indirectly cause the nucleation of carbonate minerals due to the high alkaline pH created through photosynthesis. Although no direct interaction is known, carbonate nucleation and growth occurs near the active cell surface, however through a non-organic matter related reaction depending only on the solution supersaturated conditions.

2.6 Dissolution of basaltic glass in closed flow through reactors

Quantifying the mineral dissolution in absence of cyanobacteria is necessary to determine the effects of *Synechococcus sp.* photosynthesis on basaltic glass dissolution as well as on the carbonate mineral precipitation.

To study basaltic glass dissolution, previously filtered in fine particles, "flow through reactors" system was preferred to "batch reactors" because their control of the solution composition has proven to be highly efficient. Indeed, it can provide better pH control, regulation of CO_2 quantity - remaining

almost constant all along the experiment -, of saturation state, and of organic production. Lastly, flow through reactor system, with inputs and outputs, best represents the natural system.

Part of this study thus relates to the quantification, the analysis as well as the control of basaltic glass dissolution. The choice to relate basaltic glass to cyanobacteria metabolism re-lies in the fact that, basaltic glass is found abundantly on the Earth's; and it has a relatively fast dissolution rate. At a temperature of 25°C and an acid pH of ± 2 , basaltic glass dissolution rates are lower than enstatite (Oelkers *et Schott*, 2001) or forsterite (Oelkers, 2001) ones but still higher than for some minerals as kaolinite (Carroll *et Walther*, 1990) or quartz (Berger *et al.*, 1994). It is therefore of utmost importance to quantify the rates of basaltic glass dissolution in the presence of cyanobacteria , in order to find a compromise between the generated alkaline pH environment and its effects on the basaltic glass dissolution rates.

Dissolution rates are dependent to pH condition, electrolyte concentration and air injection. According to Martinez *et al.* (2014), two dissolution mechanisms can occur as a function of pH. Mg site protonation needs a near-neutral pH whereas SiO_4 hydrolysis corresponds to alkaline conditions.

For a near-neutral pH (± 6.5), basaltic glass exposed to electrolyte (NaNO_3), is undergoing a protonation (i.e. an addition of H^+ proton by chemical reaction) thus creating complexes Ca-H and Mg-H. That involves the Mg-O and Ca-O elongation to which cations were already attached previously in the basaltic glass structure. It leads to the octahedral structure distortion and Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} releasing (Eq. 2).

Hydrolysis happens at alkaline conditions ($\text{pH} > 10$), with hydronium ions H_3O^+ , the strongest acid existing in water, which separates Ca^{2+} or Mg^{2+} cations from the SiO_4 tetrahedra to which they were previously attached (Eq. 3). This mechanism thus enhances release of SiO_4 tetrahedra buffering the bulk solution pH to 9.5.

By varying the electrolyte's concentration, the process is affected. Indeed, the higher the NaNO_3 concentration is, the more likely they are to be released from the SiO_4 tetrahedrons, and thus to increase alkalinity, leading to new cations releasing. Cyanobacteria are also expected to have an influence on the basaltic glass dissolution. Creating an alkaline micro-environment, they may enhance basaltic glass hydrolysis. In another hand, organic matter bonding to the rock risks to prevent basaltic glass from dissolution. Combining an inorganic stock with sufficient dissolved Ca^{2+} or Mg^{2+} from the basaltic glass and another stock containing active cyanobacteria at alkaline conditions, supersaturation state may be reach with respect to calcium or magnesium carbonate (Martinez *et al.*, 2014).

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1 Sample preparation

3.1.1 Basaltic glass

The study is based on a constant supply of Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} leading to biomineralization. It is important to use a natural and accessible source of those metallic cations. Basaltic glass from Skaftafell (Iceland) has been chosen.

The exact composition of this basaltic glass has to be known. A fusion machine permits to melt a sample of rock in order to analyze it with X-ray fluorescence (XRF). The fusion needs:

- 1 g of basaltic glass;
- 4 g of lithiumometaborate.

The fusion machine automatically melts elements with a mix of three gases: propane, oxygen and compressed air. For this process 10 min of pre-melting phase and 10 min of melting-phase are needed to melt the rock in the recipient composed of 90% platinum and 10% gold. The fine disc obtained from cooling the melt is analyzed by XRF machine. The result of the composition is given as an ICPW norm according to elements proportions in the basaltic glass (Annex 1).

Prepared basaltic glass was used in inorganic stocks for AFT (Active cyanobacteria Flow Through) experiment. Two separate stocks were prepared from which solution was input into the flow through reactor set-ups. One was the inorganic stock containing the basaltic glass, and the second contained the cyanobacteria suspension of either living or dead cells. As the goal of the experiments was to quantify the effect of cyanobacteria on basaltic glass dissolution, the two solutions had to be kept separate and mixed at a constant rate inside the flow through mixed reactor.

A 5 L inorganic stock is composed of:

- 3.25 g of NaNO_3 ;
- 0.375 g of MgSO_4 ;
- 20 g of basaltic glass.

This stock was constantly injected with air for a few days in order to obtain a sufficient amount of Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} cations, and dissolved carbonic acid for the experiments.

Another type of inorganic stock was used for the CFF (Calcite Flow Trough) experiment. Basaltic glass was replaced by 10g of calcium chlorid CaCl for 5 L to guarantee a sufficient calcium cations concentration.

3.1.2 Active cyanobacteria stock

Active cyanobacteria stocks are prepared in order to achieve photosynthesis in presence of basaltic glass, so as cyanobacteria influence in dissolution could be observed and supersaturation conditions reached.

A 5 L cyanobacteria stock was inoculated and grown to the stationary growth phase and then used for experiments. This stock included the following components:

- A 10 mL aliquot of BG-11 50x freshwater cyanobacteria growth medium (Sigma Aldrich® C3062). This solution is a 50x concentrate of the cyanobacteria natural living freshwater environment. A dilution of 1/500 of the above medium was generated in our experiments in order to minimize the effects of phosphate which could compromise the experiment, by affecting the process of carbonate mineral formation. The medium must be manipulated under a flame from a Bunsen burner in order to maintain sterile conditions.
- 3.25 g of sodium nitrate NaNO_3 ;
- 0.375 g of magnesium sulfate MgSO_4 ;
- 20 mL of a *Synechococcus* cyanobacteria active stock at the stationary phase.

The stock is then filled with distilled water at a conductivity of $0.055 \mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$, and bubbled with air using an aquarium pump. The air bubbling is needed to provide cyanobacteria with the needed inorganic carbon and to keep them in a constant movement, needed to live and reproduce. The stock is ready for the experiments when the quantity of cyanobacteria reaches the population stationary phase.

3.1.3 Dead cyanobacteria stock

In order to better answer the problematic of biomineralization, activity or inactivity of cyanobacteria must be taken into account. A suspension of dead cyanobacteria was prepared to be used in the CFF (Calcite Flow Through) experiment.

A 60 mL recipient is filled with a sample of an active cyanobacteria stock and immersed into 300 mL of water inside an autoclave. Active cyanobacteria are then autoclaved for 20 min at 121°C and made currently inactivated. The brown sample color marks the cell's inactivity. However a loss of material can occur during the process. In order to prevent this, 60 mL of sample are used to obtain at least the 40 mL needed to the DBF experiment.

Dead cyanobacteria are introduced into a 5 L container where the following components had been previously added:

- 3.25 g of NaNO_3 ;
- 0.375 of MgSO_4 ;
- Distilled water to complete.

The stock is then bubbled with constant air injection in order to prevent dead cyanobacteria deposition in the reactor and to maintain the same conditions as those as active cyanobacteria experiments for control.

3.2 Experimental design

3.2.1 BG 1 –BG2 (Basaltic Glass)

The experiment goal is to quantify the Mg^{2+} and Ca^{2+} rate of dissolution under inorganic conditions. Basaltic glass stocks were prepared in 5 L containers each and with respective concentrations of 0.001, 0.01, 0.1 mol/L $NaNO_3$ solutions. These supplied 6 reactors via a 12X channel peristaltic pump, ISMATEC IP 65, having a very low flow rate of 0.56 $\mu L/min$. All these reactors were closed (Figure 10).

First of all, in each reactor, a free floating magnetic stirrer is placed, resting on magnetized magnetic support, at 250 rpm, while constantly moving the solution. Then, 0.6 g of fine basaltic glass particles previously sieved to achieve a particle size range of 36 to and 63 μm (Moser, 2013), were inserted in 150 mL of electrolyte solution, present in the reactor. Solutions were pumped to the reactors. Flows move through tubes Tygon R 3603 brand with a ten centimeter length by reactor both sides, an external diameter of 4.0 mm, an internal diameter of 2.4 mm.

Figure 10 - Schematic figure of the organization of the BG1-BG2 experimental set up

3.2.2 AFT1 – AFT2 (Active cyanobacteria Flow Through reactors)

The experiment aimed at mixing two different stock solutions inside the flow through reactors. The first one was a stock of active cyanobacteria, and the second one, a stock known as “inorganic”. The 2 various stocks preparation of 5L each is explained in section 3.1. These stocks were under constant air injection by a bubbling mechanism through an aquarium pump (Figure 11).

Tygon R 3603 tubes are inserted into these two stocks with external diameter of 4.0 mm, and internal diameter of 2.4 mm. These tubes are connected tethering a 4 channels peristaltic pump Ismatec, with a very low flow rate of 1.39 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$. They permit to connect stocks with 2 reactors of 19 cL which remain closed throughout the experiment. The samples are directly taken, once daily, from the output, to measure various parameters as pH, conductivity, alkalinity, optical density, and Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} concentrations in the solution. The samples were collected within a Greiner polypropylene tube with a volume of 50 mL. In both reactors, as well as into inorganic stock, magnetic stirrers are inserted, resting on magnetic support, at 200 rpm, while constantly moving the solution. Finally, a white fluorescent light, emitting a standard light solar ray, is placed above the experiment. This light is required so that active cyanobacteria may survive.

Figure 11 - Schematic figure of the organization of the AFT1-AFT2 experimental set up

3.2.3 CFF (Calcite Flow Through) – Dead cyanobacteria experiment

The experiment was aimed at connecting, in two different reactors, an inorganic stock containing dissolved calcium cations from calcium chlorid CaCl with an inactive cyanobacteria stock, in order to observe the role of dead cells in a hypothetical bio-mineralization. The two stocks preparation of 5L each is explained in “Sample preparation”. Are then inserted into these 2 stocks Tygon R 3603 tubes with an external diameter of 4.0 mm and an internal diameter of 2.4 mm. These

tubes are connected via a 4X channels peristaltic pump Ismatec, with a translucent reactor of 19 cL. The reactor remains closed throughout the experiment (Figure 12).

The samples are directly taken, once daily, from the output, to measure various parameters as pH, conductivity, alkalinity, optical density, and Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} rates measurement in the solution. The samples were collected within a Greiner polypropylene tube with a volume of 50 mL (Moser, 2013). The reactor is placed in a water container at 22°C to keep at constant temperature the closed reactor.

Figure 12 : Schematic figure of the organization of the DFT experimental set up

3.3 Sample analysis

pH and alkalinity from samples were measured with a titration machine Metrohm 719 S Titrimo, with a maximum permissible uncertainty of $\pm 0.5\%$ (Moser, 2013). Titrations were done on approximately 20 mL of sample tanks to the TriNet software of Methrom. Conductivity was measured thanks to a Metrohm 712 conductivity meter. Calcium and magnesium concentration were measured using flame atomic absorption spectroscopy via an Analytik Jena Vario 6 (Flame AAS).

3.3.1 Spectrophotometry

Braslavsky (2006) defines the absorbance (or optical density) as the ratio logarithm of an incoming and a transmitted radiation through a material:

$$A = \log_{10} (I_0/I) \quad (4)$$

Where I_0 is the initial radiation passing through the material, and I the light that has passed through the material at a specified wavelength.

Figure 13 – A simple scheme that illustrates the basics of UV-VIS spectrophotometer

Figure 13 shows the UV-VIS spectrophotometer process (Ultraviolet – Visible Spectrophotometer) which permits to measure optical density. An incoming light at wavelength of 750 nm is sent through the cyanobacteria samples. Photons on the exit of the system have a different frequency than in the entrance. This difference gives the absorbance of the sample. This measure corresponds to the quantity of cyanobacteria in the sample. The more increasing is the optical density, the more growing is the population. Measures will be done until the absorbance becomes stable, showing a saturated cyanobacteria population (Figure 14).

Figure 14 - Absorbance in a function of time (Modified after Moser, 2010)

3.3.2 Vacuum filtration

Vacuum filtration (Figure 15) is a process used to calculate the cyanobacteria mass. First, a sample of 25 mL is collected from the active cyanobacteria stock with a Greiner polypropylene tube. The empty tube (1) is carefully weighed as well as the sample (2) and filter (3). Sample mass (2) is then deducted from the filled tube mass (1), so as to know the exact cyanobacteria mass contained in the collected sample (2). The sample is being filtered with a Whatman filter composed of cellulose nitrate, and 0.2 μm pore size. The whole manipulation is made under vacuum conditions for faster results. At the filtration end, all the cyanobacteria are contained in the filter. The remaining matter is placed in an oven at 60°C during 30 min and is carefully weighed when dried. To know the cyanobacteria exact

mass, the initial filter mass (3) is deducted from the cyanobacteria filter mass (4). Knowing the exact sample volume, a result in mass per liter can be given (mg/L).

Figure 15 - Vacuum filtration method (modified after Martinez *et al.*, 2010)

3.3.3 pH metry - Alkalinity

pH metry and alkalinity are both linked notions measured by a single machine : the 719 Titrino. Using the Tinet 2.5 program on computer, the machine can quantify the amount of OH^- and H^+ to determine the pH of the solution. The given value qualifies the solution as acid if protons are present in majority (0 to 7), or alkaline in the case of hydroxide ions (7 to 14) (Harris, 2010). Alkalinity can then be measured from pH with the same machine.

Alkalinity is the quantitative capacity of water to accept proton and it is also the sum of all bases present in order to neutralize acid in solution. The two different factors that define alkalinity are total alkalinity and carbonate alkalinity. The total alkalinity gives a measure of the total dissolved inorganic carbon (DIC) and carbonate alkalinity measures how much CO_3^{2-} are present in solution.

Alkaline compounds in this solution are in major extent, the bicarbonate ion HCO_3^- and, to minor, the carbonate ion CO_3^{2-} .

$$\text{Total alkalinity} = [\text{HCO}_3^-] + 2 [\text{CO}_3^{2-}] + [\text{OH}^-] - [\text{H}^+] \quad (5)$$

For near-neutral pH, $[\text{CO}_3^{2-}]$ and $[\text{OH}^-]$ became negligible in comparison to $[\text{HCO}_3^-]$ and $[\text{H}^+]$ concentration. Equation thus becomes:

$$\text{Total alkalinity} = [\text{HCO}_3^-] - [\text{H}^+] \quad (6)$$

The aim of titration, with a HCl concentration of 0.1 mol/L, is the proton H^+ releasing, which is consumed by the carbonates species (Moser, 2013). Any acid added would cause an immediate change in the pH, and permit, to calculate the amount, in mL, of used stock acid. The amount of acid added in order to make alkaline compounds used up, are reached for a pH of 8.3 for carbon alkalinity (CO_3^{2-}) and 4.3, more or less, for total alkalinity (HCO_3^{2-}). This particular pH is called endpoints. The second endpoint pH 4.3 represents protonation of all bicarbonate ions to carbonic acid (H_2CO_3).

3.3.4 Conductivity – Activity

Conductivity is the ability of a solution to carry an electric current. The SI unit is Siemens per meter (S/m) (Harris, 2010). The conductivity meter permits to measure it precisely.

In contrast to solids, aqueous solutions need ions to conduct electricity. The more ions the solution is composed of, the more electricity it carries and the higher the conductivity is. Ionic strength (IS) is a quantification of the amount of present dissolved salts which can be determined from conductivity (Martinez et al., 2010).

This IS is necessary to have the exact cation activity in solution. Indeed the activity a_c of a chemical species **C** corresponds to:

$$a_c = [C] \gamma_c \quad (7)$$

Where [C] is the concentration of the species and γ_c the activity coefficient defined by :

$$\log \gamma_c = (-0.51 * z^2 * \text{VIS}) / (1 + (\alpha * \text{VIS} / 305)) \quad (8)$$

Where z is the charge of the ion (e.g: Ca^{2+} , $z=2$), α the radius of the ion in picometers (e.g: $r_{\text{Ca}^{2+}} = 600$ pm) and IS the ionic strength (Stumm et Morgan, 1996).

3.3.5 Saturation state – Saturation index

The activity measures lead by calculation to the saturation state (Ω). According to Langdon (2000), this value corresponds to the potential for a mineral to form into a solution. In the case of a calcification:

$$\Omega = (a_{\text{Ca}^{2+}} * a_{\text{CO}_3^{2-}}) / K_{\text{sp}} \quad (9)$$

Where K_{sp} is the solubility product (e.g: calcite, $K_{\text{sp}}=10^{-8.48}$) and $a_{\text{Ca}^{2+}}$, $a_{\text{CO}_3^{2-}}$ activities of Ca^{2+} and CO_3^{2-} .

From saturation state, the saturation index (SI) can be calculated, which shows the chance of precipitation:

$$\text{SI} = \log(\Omega) \quad (10)$$

For positive ion activity product, Ω is >1 and $\text{SI}>0$. In the actual experiment, a positive SI would lead to a calcite precipitation (Langdon, 2000).

3.3.6 Quantifying carbonate precipitation

The transition state theory gives an estimation of the precipitated carbonate quantity from saturation state (Pechukas, 1981). The rate of calcite precipitation can be calculated as:

$$R = K^+[\text{CaL}](\Omega-1)^n \quad (11)$$

With [CaL] the concentration of Ca bound to the cell surface and K^+ and n optimizable parameters, regarding to the actual experiment.

3.3.7 Atomic Adsorption Spectroscopy

Figure 16 – Simple scheme that illustrates the basics of Flame atomic absorption spectroscopy via an Analytik Jena Vario 6 (Flame AAS).

Flame atomic absorption spectroscopy (F-AAS) method has been used to determinate the calcium and magnesium concentrations contained in a sample. The method makes use of a flame to atomize sample. If the sample is irradiated with specific wavelengths, Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} cations will absorb some of the radiation by excitation of the electrons. Therefore, a quantitative analysis is possible because of the absorbance being proportional to the population density of cations in the flame.

3.3.8 Inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry:

Inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry, is a quantification technique based on ion mass spectroscopy analysis generated by inductively coupled plasma. In the dissolved phase, the detection limits are in the ng/L range. That is the only atomic spectrometry technique to be able to provide isotopic information. In this case, ICP-MS is *thermos scientific XSERIES 2 ICP-MS* and the software is *thermos plamaLab*. There are 2 main steps for measuring: first step is to atomize and ionize elements by the plasma (argon flame from 6000 to 10000 kelvin). Second step is a method for separating ions with respect to mass. Sample preparation is an initial samples dilution of 1 in 5 mL with 3.9 mL of HNO_3^- solvent (concentration of 1%) and also, 0.1 mL of Indium internal standard IS (concentration of 250 ppb). Before starting to measure the samples, optimizing apparatus is necessary, using 8 different calibration samples respectively corresponding to different rare earth.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Three separate types of experiments were made in order to understand cyanobacteria biomineralization in presence of basaltic glass. Inorganic experiment (BG2) permits to have an overview of basaltic glass dissolution under different ionic strengths. Organic experiment (AFT2) gives the amount of cations used by active cyanobacteria for a probable precipitation. The last experiment (CFF) shows if biomineralization can be observed in presence of dead cyanobacteria. Several parameters have been measured for all experiments such as pH, total alkalinity, Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} concentration and saturation index SI. Those measures would permit to know the optimum conditions to precipitate calcite or magnesite. Air bubbling was used in some experiments to simulate natural conditions and get more significant results.

4.1 Growth Curve Stock

Growth curve of cyanobacteria stock comes from the active cyanobacteria stock used for the Active Flow Through reactor experiments (AFT2) where an active cyanobacteria stock is connected to an inorganic stock containing basaltic glass. The aim is to quantify the rate of Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} release from the basaltic glass minerals in presence of metabolically active cyanobacteria, then, determining the role of the cyanobacteria stock as passive nucleation sites with Mg^{2+} or Ca^{2+} surface organic groups complexation.

The goal of this part is to monitor the environmental conditions of the cyanobacteria stock; factors taken into account include a constant light intensity of 6000 lx, a constant temperature of more or less 23°C, and a constant supply of oxygen. Furthermore, thanks to the results of the measurements obtained, it's possible to know the point where both growth and mortality rates are in equilibrium, showing a constant biomass. From this moment, the Active Flow Through reactor experiment can be started.

Concerning the experiment execution, sample of approximately 5 mL have been taken from the cyanobacteria stock with a syringe. Then, samples were diluted and adsorption measured via UV-Vis spectroscopy. In the same case, 3 samples of 5mL each, from each cyanobacteria stock, have been taken in early, mid and late of AFT experiments. Thanks to the vacuum filtration (3.3.2) their masses could have been recorded.

Figure 17 – Growth Curve stock of the 4 *synechococcus cyanobacteria* stock in preparation of the AFT1 – AFT2 experiments.

Annex 2 shows the measurement of optical density for the whole cyanobacteria stock. Figure 17 also reveals a constant biomass after 235 hours. The growth curve remains almost stable and varies weakly. This can be explained by various processes. One of them is the active cyanobacteria death, thus providing nutrients. In addition, the cyanobacteria dying give space to others, so active cyanobacteria continue to develop. According to this process, the overall biomass remains constant. The second process lies in the fact that the viscosity increased due to the growing number of cyanobacteria inside, and thus making the medium mix by the air bubbled difficult. This is the second hypothesis that can cause a constant biomass.

Submissions are subject to potential errors made by the decrease of the cyanobacteria stock volume. Indeed, the sampling causes the decrease of the volume. That has the effect to influence the concentration making the experimental data worthless.

Considering the influence of other factors, as the natural daylight, the experiment has not been well protected against other light sources.

These factors have been critical to the development of the cyanobacteria stock; this becomes particularly effective on the data results.

4.2 Inorganic control experiment BG2

Results of basaltic glass dissolution are shown in figures 18, 19 and 20 below. Three different electrolyte solutions have been used. This figure shows the evolution of pH, total alkalinity, Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} concentrations, and saturation index (SI) for both calcite and magnesite. Those parameters are measured in presence of basaltic glass in three different reactors with respective ionic strength of 0.001 mol/L, 0.01 mol/L and 0.1 mol/L of NaNO_3 . All corresponding values are respectively showed in annexes 3, 4 and 5.

In the whole experiment and for any electrolyte concentration, pH stays globally acidic and constant between 5 and 6. This acid pH proves that this experiment won't lead to any precipitation of calcite or magnesite. Indeed, the process of biomineralization needs an alkaline pH to happen as the release of hydroxide ions OH^- permits the deprotonation of HCO_3^- to CO_3^{2-} . Furthermore, the formation of 1 mole of CaCO_3 would need the consumption of two alkalinity moles, leading to a decreasing pH in the solution (Kamennaya *et al.*, 2012) which is not notice on those experiments.

Total alkalinity remains low for the three concentrations between 0.05 and 0.1 mmol/L. Total alkalinity is equal to $[\text{HCO}_3^-] + 2[\text{CO}_3^{2-}] + [\text{OH}^-] - \text{H}^+$. It is possible to not consider CO_3^{2-} , as well as, OH^- due to the neutral pH, and total alkalinity will depend only on the concentration of bicarbonate ions (Moser, 2013). However, the more important the NaNO_3 concentration is, the higher is the total alkalinity. Some other molecules may have an important influence in the total alkalinity measurement. For instance, an important electrolyte concentration should lead to the release of Si tetrahedra in the solution. Si concentration measures have been also realized. Figure (18) shows this evolution over the experiments.

For a nominal electrolyte background of 0.001 mol/L NaNO_3 corresponds the higher Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} concentrations: respectively 0.7 mg/L and 0.06 mg/L. Those values remain constant for 200 hours, and then decrease at a lower value of 0.05 mg/L for Ca^{2+} and 0.004 mg/L for Mg^{2+} . This threshold is also reached by the other reactors with higher ionic strength (0.01 ad 0.1 mg/L). After \pm 275 hours, the concentrations decrease to the same level than for the 0.001 mol/L NaNO_3 experiment. Those results go against the typical way where NaNO_3 enhance Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} release in the solution. Higher values are observed for the first 100 hours. But the released cations is quickly diluted by the pumps and thrown out of the system, which is marked by the important concentration decrease in the figures (19).

The higher the electrolyte background is, the less concentrate Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} are at the beginning of the experiment (respectively 0.1 mg/L and 0.02 mg/L for 0.1 mol/L NaNO_3). Moser (2013) showed that NaNO_3 enhance dissolution, whereas, NaNO_3 in excess inhibit Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} released from the basaltic glass surface. This could be explained by neutral pH which is another obstacle to calcite or magnesite precipitation. It leads to two different mechanism of dissolution:

- Protonation which happens at low pH and tends to enhance Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} release.
- Hydrolysis at an alkaline pH which prevents those releases and enhances SI release.

Adding both mechanism cause incapacitation and consequently, neutral pH.

Figure 18 - Results of BG2-experiment: pH, and total alkalinity vs time for different electrolyte concentration of NaNO₃ in presence of basaltic glass.

Figure 19 - Results of BG2 experiment: Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺ concentration for different electrolyte concentration of NaNO₃ in present of basaltic glass

Figure 20 – Results of BG2 experiment: Saturation index of calcite and magnesite for different electrolyte concentration of NaNO₃ in presence of basaltic glass.

Figure 20 shows the saturation index (SI) evolution during the experiment with respect to calcite and magnesite. For the three ionic strength, conditions are closer to precipitate calcite (with a SI between -6 and -9) than magnesite (-10 to -13). Those values are relative to the Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} activities.

Those control experiments have shown that the system has to be improved in order to avoid cations waste and to increase the chance of calcite and magnesite precipitation. On another hand, neutral pH can hardly be modified, because of further experiments with cyanobacteria. Indeed, an acidic pH could lead to the death of those cyanobacteria.

4.3 Organic experiment with active cyanobacteria (AFT2)

The next figure (21) shows, Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} concentrations, total alkalinity, pH, and finally, saturation index of magnesite and calcite versus time. The background electrolyte concentration is 0.04 mol of NaNO_3 for both reactors. All values are shown in annex 6.

Mg^{2+} concentration remains constant over the whole experiment with a threshold at 3.5 mg/L. Ca^{2+} concentration values point to an average of more or less 3 mg/L. The reactor 1 has its concentration of Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} decreasing over a period of 80 hours approximately, probably because a problem of the flow in the experiment systems. The constant flow through the open system leads automatically to the dilution of dissolved cations from the inorganic stock previously prepared. The first reactor flow may be faster than the second one, and this could explain Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} concentration decrease. In order to prevent our stocks from lower cations concentration, active cyanobacteria have been put in a different stock, as organic matter tends to inhibit cations dissolution.

Total alkalinity increases from 1 mmol/L at the beginning of the experiment to reach a 1.8 mmol/L threshold at 242 hours. This increase relates to the photosynthetic activity of the cell, which consumes HCO_3^- ions and then deprotonates the HCO_3^- to CO_3^{2-} . That's causing the outer release of OH^- , and this leads to the development of an alkaline microenvironment at the cell surface. The microenvironment is surrounding each cell by a thin film of bound water molecules referred to as a hydrodynamic boundary layer (Moser, 2013). Physicochemical properties are different into the microenvironment than in the whole reactors. Furthermore, total alkalinity reaches a 1.8 mmol/L threshold, and doesn't still increase due to a decrease in pH. This is probably due to the cyanobacterial activity less important as demonstrated by the pH which is getting less basic.

pH is very high at the start of the experiment with a pH of 10.9 ± 1 , and declined throughout a period of 150 hours until a value of 10.1. This decrease can be explained by a reduced activity of the photosynthetic cyanobacteria over time. Indeed, active cyanobacteria tend to become inactive. This effectively reduces all the cyanobacteria reactions with its external environment. The consumption of bicarbonate ions is less important, thus has a direct impact on the releasing of OH^- into the solution, and CO_3^{2-} is also considerably less prominent around the cell. According to the Bjerrum plot (Figure 4), a decreasing pH may lead to a more important HCO_3^- concentration. As bicarbonate ions are a major part of the alkalinity, increasing $[\text{HCO}_3^-]$ can explain the rise of alkalinity.

Figure 21 – Results of AFT2 experiment: pH, total alkalinity, Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺ concentration and saturation index for calcite and magnesite versus time for different electrolyte concentration of NaNO₃ in presence of basaltic glass and active cyanobacteria.

Saturation index SI values remain negative for all the experiment. When SI values are below 1, there is no calcite or magnesite precipitation. SI (calcite) is higher than the SI (magnesite) and growing at a faster rate. SI for calcite increases from the beginning of the experiment at - 10.6 to - 9.4 over a period of 145 hours, whereas, SI for magnesite increases over the same times period, from -13.6 to - 12.5. Saturation index depends on metal cations (Ca^{2+} or Mg^{2+}) and CO_3^{2-} activities (Eq. 9 - 10). As Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} concentrations remain constant and CO_3^{2-} increase in concentration, a more important deprotonation of HCO_3^- is expected around cyanobacteria. This induces an important consumption of hydroxide ion OH^- which explains the decreasing pH. Increasing $[\text{CO}_3^{2-}]$ thus explain SI higher values for both calcite and magnesite.

Nevertheless, saturation index is still very low because of Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} concentrations which are very small: around 3 mg/L for Ca^{2+} concentration and 3.5 mg/L for Mg^{2+} concentration. It indicates that dissolution rate are not high enough to permit Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} release in solution, in order to reach biomineralization . SI is also very low because the occurrence of NaNO_3 tends to inhibit calcite and magnesite precipitation on active or inactive cyanobacteria. Therefore, SI remains low during all the experiment due to both explanations.

4.4 Dead cyanobacteria flow through reactor experiment in presence of calcium chlorid (CFF)

CFF experiment was expected as preliminary set-up to observe the behavior of Ca^{2+} in the presence of dead biomass and a sufficient source of calcium. This experiment consisted in an inorganic stock containing dissolved calcium chlorid, connected to an organic stock with dead cyanobacteria autoclaved at 120°C. Both inorganic and organic stock contained 3.25 g of NaNO_3 . All the experiments were performed at a nominal electrolyte background concentration of 0.04 mol/L. A reaction between the solution resulting from calcium chlorid dissolution and the dead organic matter was expected in the reactor were the two stocks were mixed. As mentioned previously, the surface charge of dead cyanobacteria is negative. Dead cells then tend to attracts cations in solution whereas active cyanobacteria protect against cations binding on their surface by generating a positive surface charge. In the context of the CFF experiment, dead cells were expected to act as nucleation sites for calcite and magnesite as cations will bind their negative surface charge leading to carbonate mineral nucleation upon the presence of sufficient carbonate species. All values corresponding to this experiment can be found in annex 7. Figure 22 shows evolution of pH, Total alkalinity, Ca^{2+} and SI (calcite) evolution versus time.

pH and total alkalinity increase through the whole experiment. Indeed, total alkalinity rises from 0.2 to 0.75 mmol/L. pH remains quite neutral but rises from 6.3 to 6.75. Dead cyanobacteria biomass has been shown to increase the pH and the total alkalinity of solutions by the interaction of their deprotonated cell surface groups with dissolving CO_2 from air injection (Martinez *et al.*, 2015). However near-neutral pH provide from any calcite precipitation as biomineralization needs an alkaline pH (at least >8).

Dissolved Ca^{2+} concentration from calcium chlorid rises as a function of time. Calcium chlorid is a calcium salt very soluble in water. Its use makes the input of calcium cations very high. Indeed the Ca^{2+} concentration is increasing from 270 mg/L to 295 mg/L. A decreasing calcium concentration would lead to the conclusion of a sorption process of Ca^{2+} in the presence of dead biomass. This phenomenon has not been observed. Therefore Ca^{2+} from basaltic glass will not be complexed by dead organic matter in a further experiment. Saturation state with respect to carbonate would be feasible in the presence of basaltic glass and dead cyanobacteria.

Saturation index values are negative but closer to the supersaturation state than for other experiments. Indeed, values are remaining at approximately -4.6 to -4.9. The presence of dead cyanobacteria enhances the chance of precipitation by increasing the SI, but values stay far from a positive saturation index. Sufficient Ca^{2+} and/or Mg^{2+} , as well as longer time span, will be required to observe carbonate mineral nucleation on the dead biomass surface. For optimum conditions, dead cyanobacteria are expected to assimilate Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} on their surface functional groups, and by doing so, initiate nucleation though an increment in the total alkalinity and the concentration of HCO_3^- near their surface.

CONCLUSION

Several conditions were tested in the aim of reaching carbonate precipitation in presence of basaltic glass as a source of metal cations (e.g. Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+}). Inorganic experiment was used to observe calcium and magnesium dissolution rates. Active cyanobacteria experiment (AFT2) results were expected to get closer to supersaturation state than inorganic experiment, as cyanobacteria photosynthesis global mechanism helps by enhancing pH and thus favors carbonate nucleation.

Inorganic experiment BG2 showed insufficient cations dissolution rates for calcium and magnesium. Nominal electrolyte background seems to be in cause, preventing basaltic glass from dissolution for high NaNO_3 concentration. Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} higher concentrations correspond to an electrolyte background of 0.001 NaNO_3 mg/L. In absence of cyanobacteria, saturation index remains negative as pH is too low for any carbonate precipitation.

Supersaturation state wasn't reach even in presence of active cyanobacteria. Although SI values were closer to 0 than for BG2 experiment, several parameters have to be improved to nucleate carbonate. pH values were well enhance by cyanobacteria metabolism, but Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} concentrations were too low, and quite decreasing through the experiment. The flow through reactor system was in cause, diluting metal cations and wasting them by the output of the open system, though it is necessary to get closer to natural conditions. Further experiments will have to improve preparation of inorganic stocks so as dissolved Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} concentration from the basaltic glass can be sufficient to reach a positive SI. In addition, an alkaline pH (at least >8) is also necessary to get to nucleation. Longer growing phase preparation should be done for active cyanobacteria stock in order to have optimal cyanobacteria saturation rates. Indeed, the more cyanobacteria is present, the more bicarbonate ions is consumed by photosynthesis, leading to the acidification of the system and the CO_3^{2-} formation, in order to reach a positive SI.

Dead cyanobacteria use has been shown to increase the saturation index of the solution. Indeed, they may act as nucleation site, binding Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} on their surface. However, presence of active cyanobacteria should be required in order to enhance pH solution to an alkaline environment. Further experiment using dead cyanobacteria in presence of basaltic glass as a source of metal cations should be done.

Though basaltic glass is abundant on the Earth's surface, it has been shown that dissolution rates at near-neutral pH are lower than for olivine (Moser, 2013). Optimal conditions like electrolyte background concentration or pH, have to be improved in order to use basaltic glass as a sufficient dissolved Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} source. In comparison, olivine or enstatite seems more appropriate to use for this type of experiment (Oelker, 2001).

In the aim of using cyanobacteria induced biomineralization for CO_2 storage at a large scale, an abundant source of Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} with a sufficient dissolution rate has to be used. Combining to massive cyanobacteria stocks, this method may permit to stock some significant rates of CO_2 .

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ANNEXES

ANNEX 1 – Basaltic glass ICPW norm

Component	Value	Unit
SiO ₂	47.61	%
TiO ₂	1.53	%
Al ₂ O ₃	14.00	%
Fe ₂ O ₃ tot	12.12	%
MnO	0.19	%
MgO	10.19	%
CaO	11.78	%
Na ₂ O	1.86	%
K ₂ O	0.26	%
P ₂ O ₅	0.19	%
SUM HE	99.73	%
V	287	ppm
Cr	627	ppm
Ni	216	ppm
Cu	151	ppm
Zn	87	ppm
Rb	5	Ppm
Sr	187	ppm
Zr	94	ppm
Ba	77	ppm

ANNEX 2 – Growth Curve Stock data

Growth curve stock 1 - 2,09 - 5L		
Date	Time (hs)	OD
02.09.2014	0	0,0383
03.09.2014	22	0,0516
04.09.2014	43	0,05935
05.09.2014	71,5	0,07995
08.09.2014	144,8	0,4281
09.09.2014	166,8	0,6267
10.09.2014	189,8	0,8262
11.09.2014	221,1	0,99125
12.09.2014	245,1	1,293
Growth curve stock 2 - 15,09 - 5L		
Date	Time (hs)	OD
15.09.2014	0	0,03865
16.09.2014	18	
18.09.2014	42	0,203
19.09.2014	68,5	0,4293
22.09.2014	139	0,7117
23.09.2014	163	0,8794
24.09.2014	186,5	0,99795
25.09.2014	210,5	0,956
26.09.2014	235	1,207
Growth curve stock 3 - 15,09 - 2L		
Date	Time (hs)	OD
15.09.2014	0	0,2005
16.09.2014	18	
18.09.2014	42	0,52835
19.09.2014	68,5	0,78035
22.09.2014	139	1,04375
23.09.2014	163	1,20655
24.09.2014	186,5	
25.09.2014	210,5	1,631
26.09.2014	235	1,6045
Growth curve stock 4 - 19,09 - 5L		
Date	Time (hs)	OD
19.09.2014	0	0,05295
22.09.2014	70	0,46475
23.09.2014	94	0,6729
24.09.2014	118	0,7127
25.09.2014	210,5	0,85025
26.09.2014	235	0,892

ANNEX 3 - Measurements of pH, conductivity, total alkalinity, Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺ concentration for BG2 experiment in a 0.001 mol/L NaNO₃ solution.

Condition	Sample	Time (hs)	pH	Conductivity (mS/cm)	Tot. Alk. (mmol/L)	Ionic Strength [M]	Ca (mg/L)	Mg (mg/L)	a[Ca ²⁺]	a[Mg ²⁺]	a[CO ₃ ²⁻]	SI (Calcite)	SI (Magnesite)
0.001 M NaNO ₃	BG2 2.1	0	5.56	0.1433	0.075	0.00621818	0.4511	0.05838	8.184E-06	1.76751E-06	7.4119E-11	-6.7371178	-10.71649034
slow flow rate	BG2 2.2	28.33	5.16	0.1321	0.06	0.00571866	0.6643	0.02949	1.219E-05	9.02266E-07	1.5078E-10	-6.2556493	-10.70011243
one pump	BG2 2.3	53.83	4.9	0.1308	0.055	0.00566068	0.6834	0.02727	1.256E-05	8.35394E-07	2.5187E-10	-6.0198977	-10.51070933
	BG2 2.4	76.33	5.95	0.1301	0.07	0.00562946	0.6463	0.0236	1.189E-05	7.23459E-07	2.8593E-11	-6.988738	-11.51810788
one pump	BG2 2.5	99.83	5.66	0.1313	0.065	0.00568298	0.69	0.02427	1.267E-05	7.43131E-07	5.17E-11	-6.7036467	-11.24922927
	BG2 2.6	176.13	5.54	0.1364	0.075	0.00591044	0.6051	0.02202	1.105E-05	6.70958E-07	7.8194E-11	-6.583289	-11.11391423
	BG2 2.7	195.63	5.29	0.131	0.06	0.00566696	0.2431	0.00831	4.466E-06	2.54521E-07	1.1191E-10	-6.8211888	-11.37918712
	BG2 2.8	245.13	5.17	0.1287	0.065	0.00556702	0.1814	0.00918	3.341E-06	2.81799E-07	1.6024E-10	-6.7913824	-11.17907667
	BG2 2.9	267.63	5.43	0.1292	0.065	0.00558932	0.1898	0.01779	3.494E-06	5.45833E-07	8.8008E-11	-7.0322021	-11.15220344
	BG2 2.10	341.63	5.22	0.1284	0.05	0.00555364	0.2023	0.00671	3.727E-06	2.06038E-07	1.0989E-10	-6.9076794	-11.47886361
	BG2 2.11	365.63	5.43	0.1265	0.07	0.0054689	0.07744	0.00349	1.43E-06	1.07366E-07	9.5071E-11	-7.3867497	-11.82487118
	BG2 2.12	386.13	5.67	0.1262	0.075	0.00545552	0.06846	0.00273	1.264E-06	8.40104E-08	5.8635E-11	-7.650024	-12.14129105
	BG2 2.13	410.63	4.85	0.1252	0.055	0.00541092	0.04981	0.00209	9.208E-07	6.43799E-08	2.8442E-10	-7.1018702	-11.57107055
	BG2 2.14	434.63	5.75	0.1264	0.09	0.00546444	na	na	na	na	5.8512E-11	na	na
Condition	Sample	Time (hs)	pH	Conductivity (mS/cm)	Tot. Alk. (mmol/L)	Ionic Strength [M]	Ca (mg/L)	Mg (mg/L)	a[Ca ²⁺]	a[Mg ²⁺]	a[CO ₃ ²⁻]	SI (Calcite)	SI (Magnesite)
0.001 M NaNO ₃	BG2 4.1	0	6.28	0.1445	0.095	0.0062717	0.4757	0.05405	8.62E-06	1.63463E-06	1.7867E-11	-7.3324666	-11.36832442
slow flow rate	BG2 4.2	28.33	6.03	0.1337	0.075	0.00579002	0.6789	0.03894	1.244E-05	1.18957E-06	2.5379E-11	-7.0280003	-11.35392482
one pump	BG2 4.3	53.83	5.2	0.1331	0.065	0.00576326	0.681	0.02517	1.248E-05	7.69352E-07	1.488E-10	-6.2510448	-10.77504544
	BG2 4.4	76.33	5.82	0.1313	0.085	0.00568298	0.6864	0.02267	1.279E-05	6.9414E-07	4.6773E-11	-6.7431315	-11.32234196
	BG2 4.5	99.83	5.39	0.1339	0.07	0.00579894	0.6819	0.02214	1.249E-05	6.76218E-07	1.0337E-10	-6.4090357	-10.98928603
	BG2 4.6	176.13	5.55	0.137	0.075	0.00569372	0.5647	0.02045	1.031E-05	6.22768E-07	7.6364E-11	-6.6238519	-11.15656974
	BG2 4.7	195.63	5.5	0.1312	0.075	0.00567852	0.177	0.0089	3.251E-06	2.72538E-07	8.6236E-11	-7.07228	-11.46267017
	BG2 4.8	245.13	5.7	0.129	0.08	0.0055804	0.1403	0.01045	2.563E-06	3.2069E-07	5.8183E-11	-7.3430727	-11.5629026
	BG2 4.9	267.63	5.21	0.1293	0.06	0.00559378	0.1311	0.00688	2.413E-06	2.11072E-07	1.3481E-10	-7.007753	-11.37964493
	BG2 4.10	341.63	5.03	0.1288	0.065	0.00557148	0.1645	0.00649	3.029E-06	1.99204E-07	1.8714E-10	-6.7665003	-11.26231742
	BG2 4.11	365.63	5.02	0.1267	0.06	0.00547782	0.07558	0.0023	1.395E-06	7.07428E-08	2.0941E-10	-7.0544486	-11.66310179
	BG2 4.12	386.13	5.45	0.1269	0.08	0.00548674	0.04563	na	8.42E-07	na	1.0371E-10	-7.5788598	na
	BG2 4.13	410.63	5.49	0.1263	0.08	0.00545998	0.04664	0.00256	8.991E-07	7.87711E-08	9.4654E-11	-7.5905356	-11.96127828
	BG2 4.14	434.63	5.48	0.1261	0.08	0.00545106	na	na	na	na	9.6881E-11	na	na

ANNEX 4 – Measurements of pH, conductivity, total alkalinity, Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺ concentration for BG2 experiment in a 0.01 mol/L NaNO₃ solution.

Condition	Sample	Time (hs)	pH	Conductivity (mS/cm)	Tot. Alk. (mmol/L)	Ionic Strength [M]	Ca (mg/L)	Mg (mg/L)	a(Ca ²⁺)	a(Mg ²⁺)	a(CO ₃ ²⁻)	SI (Calcite)	SI (Magnesite)
0.01 M NaNO ₃ slow flow rate one pump	BG2 1.1	0	6,25	1,166	0,095	0,0518306	0,3828	0,0632	4,572E-06	1,33144E-06	1,1996E-11	-7,7808227	-11,63042527
	BG2 1.2	28,33	5,7	1,161	0,07	0,0516076	0,2469	0,030363	2,952E-06	6,40239E-07	3,1403E-11	-7,5528609	-11,53047008
	BG2 1.3	53,83	5,84	1,162	0,085	0,0516522	0,1765	0,04531	2,11E-06	9,55241E-07	2,7617E-11	-7,7545243	-11,4124907
	BG2 1.4	76,33	5,38	1,159	0,065	0,0515184	0,2043	0,02667	2,444E-06	5,62572E-07	6,0955E-11	-7,346882	-11,29859424
	BG2 1.5	99,83	5,86	1,155	0,07	0,05134	0,1183	0,01869	1,416E-06	3,9453E-07	2,1759E-11	-8,0311468	-11,9000573
	BG2 1.6	176,13	5,48	1,172	0,085	0,0520982	0,2983	0,02135	3,558E-06	4,49297E-07	6,3105E-11	-7,1686873	-11,38118861
	BG2 1.7	195,63	5,58	1,176	0,075	0,0522766	0,1187	0,00948	1,415E-06	1,99358E-07	4,4183E-11	-7,7240722	-11,88889285
	BG2 1.8	245,13	5,68	1,161	0,085	0,0516076	0,169	0,01308	2,021E-06	2,75807E-07	3,9929E-11	-7,6131744	-11,79188613
	BG2 1.9	267,63	5,54	1,166	0,07	0,0518306	0,1543	0,01625	1,843E-06	3,42341E-07	4,5333E-11	-7,5980542	-11,64291455
	BG2 1.10	341,63	5,8	1,16	0,07	0,051563	0,4005	0,01535	4,79E-06	3,23731E-07	2,4951E-11	-7,4425714	-11,92651535
	BG2 1.11	365,63	4,88	1,158	0,06	0,0514738	0,07025	0,03242	8,406E-07	6,83985E-07	1,7798E-10	-7,3450578	-10,74837506
	BG2 1.12	386,13	5,05	1,156	0,075	0,0513846	0,06286	0,02414	7,525E-07	5,09482E-07	1,5049E-10	-7,4660027	-10,9491578
	BG2 1.13	410,63	5,44	1,152	0,085	0,0512062	0,14	0,0028	1,677E-06	5,91378E-08	6,9552E-11	-7,4530555	-12,21961181
	BG2 1.14	434,63	4,08	1,158	na	0,0514738	na	na	na	na	na	na	na
0.01 M NaNO ₃ slow flow rate one pump	BG2 3.1	0	6,22	1,159	0,09	0,0515184	0,3543	0,06756	4,238E-06	1,4251E-06	1,2199E-11	-7,8064501	-11,59359846
	BG2 3.2	28,33	5,81	1,161	0,075	0,0516076	0,1378	0,02132	1,648E-06	4,49557E-07	2,6118E-11	-7,8861695	-11,76406433
	BG2 3.3	53,83	5,4	1,161	0,06	0,0516076	0,1122	0,0135	1,342E-06	2,84663E-07	5,3706E-11	-7,6623359	-11,64942778
	BG2 3.4	76,33	5,78	1,163	0,085	0,0516988	0,1788	0,01604	2,137E-06	3,381E-07	3,1701E-11	-7,6891093	-11,80367117
	BG2 3.5	99,83	5,58	1,16	0,07	0,051563	0,1379	0,01551	1,649E-06	3,27105E-07	4,1408E-11	-7,6856097	-11,70201193
	BG2 3.6	176,13	5,85	1,164	0,095	0,0517414	0,2907	0,0165	3,474E-06	3,47733E-07	3,0148E-11	-7,4999347	-11,81327754
	BG2 3.7	195,63	5,45	1,1725	0,06	0,0521205	0,1299	0,00713	1,549E-06	1,50033E-07	4,7724E-11	-7,6511023	-11,97885938
	BG2 3.8	245,13	5,55	1,167	0,07	0,0518752	0,1126	0,00956	1,345E-06	2,01365E-07	4,4289E-11	-7,745089	-11,88350026
	BG2 3.9	267,63	5,61	1,162	0,065	0,0516522	0,08064	0,00632	9,641E-07	1,3324E-07	3,5865E-11	-7,9812241	-12,15447326
	BG2 3.10	341,63	5,2	1,164	0,055	0,0517414	0,1366	0,00648	1,632E-06	1,36564E-07	7,7965E-11	-7,41529	-11,80654739
	BG2 3.11	365,63	4,85	1,15	0,06	0,051117	0,0614	0,01317	7,36E-07	2,78261E-07	1,911E-10	-7,371864	-11,10806715
	BG2 3.12	386,13	5,01	1,154	0,06	0,0512954	0,0475	0,0092	5,689E-07	1,94239E-07	1,3207E-10	-7,6441758	-11,42463374
	BG2 3.13	410,63	5	1,149	0,055	0,0510724	0,08869	0,00625	1,063E-06	1,32076E-07	1,2405E-10	-7,3997367	-11,61936897
	BG2 3.14	434,63	5,5	1,161	0,08	0,0516076	na	na	na	na	5,6881E-11	na	na

ANNEX 5 – Measurements of pH, conductivity, total alkalinity, Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺ concentration for BG2 experiment in a 0.1 mol/L NaNO₃ solution.

Condition	Sample	Time (hs)	pH	Conductivity (mS/cm)	Tot. Alk. (mmol/L)	Ionic Strength [M]	Ca (mg/L)	Mg (mg/L)	a(Ca ²⁺)	a(Mg ²⁺)	a(CO ₃ ²⁻)	SI (Calcite)	SI (Magnesite)
0.1 M NaNO ₃	BG2 5.1	0	5.75	9.32	0.08	0.415499	0.08472	0.03211	5.574E-07	4.28876E-07	1.5069E-11	-8.595777	-12.02337668
slow flow rate	BG2 5.2	28.33	5.88	9.399	0.085	0.4190224	0.09831	0.03176	6.452E-07	4.23453E-07	1.1829E-11	-8.6373739	-12.13403256
one pump	BG2 5.3	53.83	5.95	9.301	0.085	0.4146516	0.09196	0.02682	6.054E-07	3.58373E-07	1.011E-11	-8.7332215	-12.27469123
	BG2 5.4	76.33	5.51	9.319	0.07	0.4154544	0.0853	0.03119	5.612E-07	4.16697E-07	2.2914E-11	-8.4107736	-11.85599627
	BG2 5.5	99.83	5.87	9.364	0.085	0.4174614	0.1121	0.01995	7.365E-07	2.66199E-07	1.2122E-11	-8.5692445	-12.32498679
	BG2 5.6	176.13	5.98	9.44	0.105	0.420851	0.123	0.01889	8.062E-07	2.5163E-07	1.1587E-11	-8.5496046	-12.36905784
	BG2 5.7	195.63	5.03	9.923	0.065	0.4423928	0.6403	0.2206	4.136E-06	2.9082E-06	6.267E-11	-7.1063932	-10.57309667
	BG2 5.8	245.13	5.27	9.385	0.08	0.418398	0.1023	0.02156	6.717E-07	2.87547E-07	4.5381E-11	-8.0359768	-11.71820035
	BG2 5.9	267.63	5.77	9.291	0.08	0.4142056	0.05049	0.01892	3.325E-07	2.52869E-07	1.4408E-11	-8.8396206	-12.27227417
	BG2 5.10	341.63	5.84	9.27	0.08	0.413269	0.06531	0.01239	4.304E-07	1.66673E-07	1.2275E-11	-8.7971659	-12.52552732
	BG2 5.11	366.63	5.04	9.336	0.07	0.4162126	0.04171	0.01575	2.743E-07	2.10289E-07	6.7575E-11	-8.2520304	-11.68118058
	BG2 5.12	386.13	5.38	9.365	0.08	0.417506	0.03526	0.01289	2.316E-07	1.71991E-07	3.5257E-11	-8.6079288	-12.05103386
	BG2 5.13	410.63	5.57	9.327	0.09	0.4158112	0.0443	0.00644	2.914E-07	8.60021E-08	2.5651E-11	-8.6464325	-12.49017653
	BG2 5.14	434.63	5.8	9.765	0.095	0.435346	na	na	na	na	1.5655E-11	na	na
Condition	Sample	Time (hs)	pH	Conductivity (mS/cm)	Tot. Alk. (mmol/L)	Ionic Strength [M]	Ca (mg/L)	Mg (mg/L)	a(Ca ²⁺)	a(Mg ²⁺)	a(CO ₃ ²⁻)	SI (Calcite)	SI (Magnesite)
0.1 M NaNO ₃	BG2 6.1	0	5.37	9.333	0.1	0.4160788	0.09877	0.2307	6.495E-07	3.08044E-06	4.5159E-11	-8.052647	-10.69042686
slow flow rate	BG2 6.2	28.33	5.26	9.289	0.08	0.4141164	0.08081	0.02206	5.322E-07	2.94849E-07	4.6629E-11	-8.1252961	-11.69553303
one pump	BG2 6.3	53.83	5.29	9.343	0.08	0.4165248	0.08118	0.02015	5.337E-07	2.68994E-07	4.3416E-11	-8.155055	-11.76639173
	BG2 6.4	76.33	5.33	9.262	0.08	0.4129122	0.07068	0.02167	4.659E-07	2.89813E-07	3.9733E-11	-8.2525894	-11.77251204
	BG2 6.5	99.83	5.26	9.32	0.085	0.415499	0.07704	0.02002	5.068E-07	2.67396E-07	4.9477E-11	-8.1207178	-11.71222397
	BG2 6.6	176.13	5.05	9.455	0.08	0.42152	0.09312	0.02252	6.101E-07	2.99885E-07	7.5092E-11	-7.8590433	-11.48123911
	BG2 6.7	195.63	4.94	9.325	0.07	0.4151722	0.06436	0.01028	4.234E-07	1.37289E-07	8.5112E-11	-7.9633001	-11.76615722
	BG2 6.8	245.13	5.38	8.905	0.08	0.39699	0.06152	0.01086	4.102E-07	1.46444E-07	3.597E-11	-8.3510463	-12.11216666
	BG2 6.9	267.63	5.23	8.72	0.08	0.388739	0.07239	0.01193	4.857E-07	1.61586E-07	5.1235E-11	-8.1240688	-11.91581286
	BG2 6.10	341.63	4.95	8.916	0.07	0.3974806	0.05352	0.01406	3.567E-07	1.89546E-07	8.4672E-11	-8.0399099	-11.62833108
	BG2 6.11	366.63	4.83	9.02	0.055	0.402119	0.05801	0.00813	3.853E-07	1.09335E-07	8.7297E-11	-7.9931474	-11.85402271
	BG2 6.12	386.13	5.29	8.99	0.085	0.400781	0.02386	na	1.587E-07	na	4.6842E-11	-8.6489214	na
	BG2 6.13	410.63	5.49	8.825	0.085	0.393422	0.0434	0.00573	2.902E-07	7.74143E-08	2.9774E-11	-8.5835286	-12.47113171
	BG2 6.14	434.63	5.47	9.357	0.08	0.4171492	na	na	na	na	2.8668E-11	na	na

ANNEX 6 - Measurements of pH, conductivity, total alkalinity, carbonate alkalinity, optical density, Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺ concentration for AFT2 experiment in presence of active cyanobacteria in a 0.04 mol/L NaNO₃ solution.

Sample	Time (hs)	pH	Conductivity (mS/cm)	Carb. Alk	tot Alk. (mmol/L)	OD		Ionic Strength[M]
AFT2 1.1	0	10,8	1,206	0,755	1,02	0,7196	0,7283	0,0536146
AFT2 1.2	74	10,63	1,143	0,615	0,91	0,6029	na	0,0508048
AFT2 1.3	97	10,46	1,151	0,665	1,26	0,8598	na	0,0511616
AFT2 1.4	121	10,36	1,169	0,675	1,445	1,096	na	0,0519644
Sample	Time (hs)	pH	Conductivity (mS/cm)	Carb. Alk	tot Alk. (mmol/L)	OD		Ionic Strength[M]
AFT2 2.1	0	11	1,21	0,89	1,035	0,6708	0,6765	0,053793
AFT2 2.2	74	10,57	1,149	0,67	1,095	0,7783	na	0,0510724
AFT2 2.3	97	10,53	1,143	0,66	1,14	0,8232	na	0,0508048
AFT2 2.4	121	10,43	1,158	0,77	1,54	1,012	na	0,0514738
AFT2 2.5	145,6	10,08	1,154	0,66	1,69	0,934	na	0,0512954
AFT2 2.6	242,6	10,17	1,159	0,7	1,81	1,0064	na	0,0515184
Sample	Time (hs)	Ca (mg/L)	Mg (mg/L)	a(Ca2+)	a(Mg2+)	a(CO32-)	SI (Calcite)	SI (Magnesite)
AFT2 1.1	0	5,844	3,578	6,92E-05	7,48442E-05	3,59E-15	-10,12439042	-13,40413449
AFT2 1.2	74	4,128	2,057	4,956E-05	4,35168E-05	4,82E-15	-10,14193235	-13,51217819
AFT2 1.3	97	2,892	3,354	3,466E-05	7,08516E-05	9,85E-15	-9,986824301	-12,99006293
AFT2 1.4	121	2,697	3,311	3,219E-05	6,97155E-05	1,42E-14	-9,86139065	-12,83960925
Sample	Time (hs)	Ca (mg/L)	Mg (mg/L)	a(Ca2+)	a(Mg2+)	a(CO32-)	SI (Calcite)	SI (Magnesite)
AFT2 2.1	0	3,342	3,451	3,954E-05	7,21372E-05	2,3E-15	-10,56156052	-13,61422948
AFT2 2.2	74	2,265	3,394	2,716E-05	7,17228E-05	6,65E-15	-10,26349174	-13,15548572
AFT2 2.3	97	2,741	3,412	3,291E-05	7,21824E-05	7,6E-15	-10,12189955	-13,09454
AFT2 2.4	121	3,129	3,471	3,744E-05	7,32298E-05	1,29E-14	-9,836929143	-12,85936398
AFT2 2.5	145,6	3,384	3,322	4,053E-05	7,01373E-05	3,17E-14	-9,411703619	-12,48728648
AFT2 2.6	242,6	3,302	3,402	3,95E-05	7,17611E-05	2,75E-14	-9,483608119	-12,53811773

ANNEX 7 - Measurements of pH, conductivity, total alkalinity and Ca²⁺ concentration for CFF experiment in presence of dead cyanobacteria in a 0.04 mol/L NaNO₃ solution.

Sample	Time (hs)	pH	Conductivity (mS/cm)	Total Alkalinity (mmol/L)	Ca (mg/L)	Ionic Strength [M]	a(Ca ²⁺)	a(CO ₃ ²⁻)	SI (Calcite)
CFF 1	0	6,29	2,437	0,185	272,6	0,1085172	0,002665	1,67E-11	-4,870382054
CFF 2	20,33	6,39	2,443	0,245	271,2	0,1087848	0,002649	1,76E-11	-4,851303435
CFF 3	45,83	6,35	2,45	0,27	268,4	0,109097	0,00262	2,12E-11	-4,774403954
CFF 4	68,33	6,43	2,451	0,265	276,2	0,1091416	0,002696	1,73E-11	-4,850193527
CFF 5	91,83	6,43	2,448	0,3	277,4	0,1090078	0,002708	1,96E-11	-4,79409671
CFF 6	168,13	6,46	2,466	0,36	276,1	0,1098106	0,00269	2,19E-11	-4,748982116
CFF 7	187,63	6,42	2,474	0,5	280,6	0,1101674	0,002731	3,34E-11	-4,560189988
CFF 8	237,13	6,55	2,47	0,485	287,6	0,109989	0,002801	2,4E-11	-4,692269033
CFF 9	260,73	6,47	2,485	0,515	280,4	0,110658	0,002726	3,06E-11	-4,598891231
CFF 10	334,73	6,63	2,481	0,555	287,2	0,1104796	0,002793	2,28E-11	-4,715552753
CFF 11	358,73	6,64	2,51	0,595	287	0,111773	0,002782	2,38E-11	-4,698853046
CFF 12	379,23	6,71	2,518	0,74	290,1	0,1121298	0,00281	2,52E-11	-4,670355572
CFF 13	403,73	6,74	2,526	0,635	295	0,1124866	0,002855	2,01E-11	-4,760419978
CFF 14	427,73	6,74	2,576	0,63					
CFF 15	477,73	6,87	2,642	0,57					
CFF 16	501,73	6,82	2,648	0,655					